

13th INTERNATIONAL
CONGRESS
OF THE SERBIAN SOCIETY
OF TOXICOLOGY

1st TOXSEE
REGIONAL
CONFERENCE

Present and Future of toxicology: Challenges and opportunities

10 - 12 May, 2023 Belgrade

electronic

ABSTRACT
BOOK

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DEAR COLLEAGUES, DEAR FRIENDS,

We are delighted to greet you on the **13th International Congress of the Serbian Society of Toxicology & 1. TOXSEE Regional Conference - Present and Future of toxicology: challenges and opportunities**, organized in Belgrade from 10-12 May 2023.

Five years after our last international Congress we gathered in Belgrade, to further promote contemporary toxicology, in the broadest sense of meaning, as a response to the new challenges requiring innovative approaches and solutions, as it is understood in the third decade of the XXI century.

Initial concept, to blend the top scientific level in toxicology with the potentials of its' use in broad array of clinical and other domains, proved to be right. Line-up of more than 70 first class international and regional faculties as well as best Serbian scientists and toxicology professionals in all related domains fully justify the approach. Moreover, interest and presence of more than 250 colleagues from Serbia and region witness that our professional community has recognized the approach taken and shown vast interest.

The Serbian Society of Toxicology is committed to innovation and creativity in research and education, in cooperation with collegial associations and institutions in Serbia and abroad. As a regional leader, we developed and inaugurated the regional brand TOXSEE, with the idea to gather as much as possible expertise and know-how from the region and Europe, to capture knowledge, share experience and exchange practical skills with colleagues who deal with toxicology problems daily.

Time imposes on us the need to integrate science, top knowledge and daily practice in a quality and efficient way, to contribute to the better health of the society as a whole in the most purposeful manner. Therefore, a thematic and functional connections with domains of emergency medicine, general medicine, paediatrics, ecology, in addition to already standard toxicological disciplines i.e. clinical, forensic, occupational, and experimental toxicology have been enhanced.

We are glad to host you in a pleasant atmosphere of Belgrade in mid-May, to benefit from the attractive and dynamic program, exchange knowledge, and, equally important, to refresh existing and establish new contacts with colleagues and friends, while enjoying our hospitality and cherish the moment in one of the best partying cities of Europe.

YOU ARE MOST WELCOME!!!

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- President of the 13th STC Congress

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SUICIDNOST U DOBA PANDEMIJE KORONA VIRUSOM

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Samoubistvo je svesno i namerno uništavanje sopstvenog života. Zbog porasta stope suicida među osetljivim kategorijama stanovništva, ono predstavlja značajan zdravstveni i društveni problem. Pandemija korona virusom je izložila celokupno stanovništvo brojnim neizvesnostima koje su uslovile pojavu novih i pogoršanje već postojećih psihijatrijskih fenomena među pojedincima, u koje spadaju i pokušaji samoubistva. Pretpostavlja se da će izloženost populacije višestrukim stresnim okolnostima i problemima uticati na porast stope samoubistava u doba pandemije korona virusom. Cilj istraživanja je utvrđivanje učestalosti suicidalnog ponašanja među bolesnicima lečenim na Klinici za psihijatriju Kliničkog centra Vojvodine (KCV) za vreme pandemije korona virusom i utvrđivanje psihopatoloških i sociodemografskih karakteristika ove kohortne grupe.

Istraživanje je obuhvatilo 112 bolesnika čiji anamnestički podaci, dobijeni upotrebom kliničkog informacionog sistema KCV, sadrže podatak o pokušaju suicida u 2020. godini. Ispitivana obeležja su statistički obrađena u statističkom programu JASP 0.14.1 i Microsoft Excel 2016. Rezultati su predstavljeni tabelarno i grafički. Utvrđeno je da je pokušaj suicida bio češći među osobama ženskog pola, starosti 11-24 i 35-44 godina. Ne postoji statistički značajna povezanost između suicidalnosti i COVID-19 okolnosti u ispitivanom uzorku. Najčešći metod pokušaja samoubistva je bilo namerno samotrovanje lekovima. Učestalost pokušaja suicida je bila veća u drugoj polovini godine. Pojedini bolesnici su više puta u godini pokušali da izvrše samoubistvo. Kod većine bolesnika su prisutni psihijatrijski komorbiditeti. U doba pandemije korona virusom značajna je rana dijagnoza mentalnih poremećaja, kao i održavanje kontakata u cilju prevencije pokušaja suicida među osetljivim populacionim grupama.

KLJUČNE REČI: suicid, pokušaj suicida, pandemija, samotrovanje, COVID-19

SUICIDALITY IN THE PERIOD OF CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC

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Suicide is conscious and deliberate attempt at taking one's own life. Due to the increase in suicide rates, suicide is considered a significant health and social problem. The uncertainties about coronavirus pandemic led to new and/or exacerbation of existing psychiatric problems among which are also suicide attempts. Such stress will assumably lead to an increase of suicide rates during the coronavirus pandemic. The aim of the study was to determine a frequency of suicide behavior among patients that were treated at Psychiatry Clinic at the Clinical Center of Vojvodina and to determine psychopathological and sociodemographic characteristics of this cohort. A total of 112 patients' anamnestic data that contained information about a suicide attempt in 2020 were analysed. The data were statistically analysed in JASP 0.14.1 and Microsoft Excel 2016.

The results were presented in tables and graphs. The analysis of collected data showed that suicide attempts were more frequent among female patients, 11-24 and 35-44 years old. We found no statistically significant correlation between suicidality and COVID-19 motivation for suicide attempt. The most frequent method used for attempting suicide was drug intoxication. The frequency of suicide attempts was higher in the latter half of the year. Some patients attempted suicide more than once in 2020. Most of the patients have psychiatric comorbidities. During the coronavirus pandemic, an early diagnosis of psychiatric illness is of great importance. It is also significant for vulnerable groups to stay socially engaged in order to prevent as many as possible suicide attempts.

KEYWORDS: suicide, suicide attempt, pandemic, self-poisoning, COVID-19